

РОЛЬ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВЛЕННОСТИ В СТАНОВЛЕНИИ
СПОРТИВНОГО МАСТЕРСТВА ПРИ ЗАНЯТИЯХ БОРЬБОЙ

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Аннотация: *В статье рассмотрен развитие физической подготовленности при занятиях спортом является обязательным условием для успешного совершенствования спортивного мастерства и достижения высоких результатов на соревнованиях. занятия спортом является обязательным условием для успешного совершенствования спортивного мастерства и достижения высоких результатов на соревнованиях. занятия спортом является обязательным условием для успешного совершенствования спортивного мастерства и достижения высоких результатов на соревнованиях.*

Ключевие слова: *Физической подготовленности, скоростно-силовых качеств, технико-тактических навыков, взрывной силой, гибкость, специальной выносливостью, ловкость и сила.*

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL FITNESS IN THE FORMATION OF
SPORTSMANSHIP IN WRESTLING CLASSES

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Annotation: *The article examines the development of physical fitness in sports is a prerequisite for the successful improvement of sports skills and achieving high results in competitions. sports is a prerequisite for the successful improvement of sports skills and achieving high results in competitions. sports is a prerequisite for the successful improvement of sports skills and achieving high results in competitions.*

Keywords: *Physical fitness, speed and strength qualities, technical and tactical skills, explosive strength, flexibility, special endurance, agility and strength.*

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It should be noted that in the formation of the sportsmanship of wrestlers, such quality as flexibility also acquires an important importance. Dexterity and strength are also important components of the formation of sportsmanship, and therefore the development of these qualities in wrestlers is advisable to start from the first day of training and should be continued throughout all stages of long-term sports training.

Purposeful development of physical fitness during sports is a prerequisite for successful improvement of sports skills and achieving high results at competitions. At the same time, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of speed and strength qualities as an important component not only of physical fitness, but also of the formation of technical and tactical skills [1,3].

It is known that the problem of complex development of physical qualities in the process of long-term sports training, taking into account the specifics of the sport, attracted the attention of a wide range of researchers.

(V.M.Zatsiorsky, 1970; M.A.Godik, 1977; A.A.Platonov, 1986;

Yu.V.Verkhoshansky, 1988, etc.). Moreover, the idea is put forward that in each particular sport, due to its specifics, priority physical qualities are allocated, the development of which facilitates not only the learning process, but will also stimulate the formation of sports skills. For example, when practicing wrestling, speed and strength qualities are of leading importance, which is necessary when performing techniques in the shortest possible time and with great explosive force. At the same time, during competitive fights, a wrestler often has to repeatedly perform attack, counterattack and defense techniques. Consequently, for a successful performance both during a separate bout and throughout the entire competitive cycle, a highly developed speed-power endurance is necessary. Yu.V.Verkhoshansky (1985) believes that a distinctive feature of martial arts is the performance of complex coordinated motor actions of speed-power orientation in the conditions of urgently changing duel situations. The author also provides information that the participants of the World Freestyle Wrestling Championship had a significant deterioration in the technique of performing techniques during the third period of fights. It is known that for the successful development of special endurance, including speed and strength, it is necessary that wrestlers perform special exercises in technique for a long time, and even against the background of fatigue [3,8].

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flexibility development will allow the wrestler to quickly "get away" from the "bridge" position or help to effectively make various deflection throws.

This quality usually develops with regular and prolonged use of specially directed exercises. Moreover, even if you temporarily stop the exercise on the development of flexibility, there may be a partial loss of this quality due to a deterioration in the elasticity of muscle fibers and mobility in the joints. Flexibility should be developed from a young age. Flexibility training requires extreme caution. Forced flexibility training can lead to various injuries in the joints, joint bags and tendons, and sometimes careless "stretching" leads to rupture of muscle fibers [4,5].

Dexterity and strength are also important components of the formation of sportsmanship, and therefore the development of these qualities in wrestlers is advisable to start from the first day of training and should be continued throughout all stages of long-term sports training.

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